

A Comprehensive Study on Polymer Matrix Composites for Industrial Applications

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Abstract:

The primary aim of this research is to create a novel composite material using a polymer base, which is more effective than the current polymer based composite materials in many aspects such as durability, ductility, performance-wise, cost, reliability, etc. Few of the other objectives are to study the Mech. Property of fabricated PMC's, to study the tribological property of fabricated PMC's, to study to review the study of the effects of the reinforcements on characteristics of the base materials, for studying of the microstructure of the test sample by analysing the SEM pictures. Other main objective being to develop special purpose moulds to facilitate laminate preparation to make test specimens for tensile, compression, flexural, chemical and wear tests, to fabricate composite laminates using a very good higher molecular weight based poly-ethylene fibers supplied by the manufacturer & conduct series of tensile, compression and flexure tests, to conduct wear tests on thermoset polymer resin reinforced with ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene fibers. The primary reinforcements for the composite material consist of surface-treated ultra-high molecular weight based polyethylene fibers, which have been acquired through external sources. Surface's modification of the reinforcement system is expected to bring in dramatic improvements in the overall performance of different PMCs, in view of the different physical property such as the Abrasion resistance, Tear resistance, Coefficient of friction, Water absorption, Density reduction, Modulus enhancement, Compression set resistance, Barrier properties and hardness.

Keywords - Low Density Polyethylene, Polyethylene, Fibers, Reinforcement, Polymer Matrix Composite, Coconut Fibre, Flexure, Stresses, Strains, Water Absorptivity, Electrical, Mechanical Properties.

1.Introduction

Polymer matrix composites have emerged as the vital & most promised materials for a larger category of application because of their excellent mechanical, physical, and chemical properties. These composite materials could be utilized in different companies, viz., automotive, aerospace companies, marine, construction, and sports equipment. Among these, fibre-reinforced polymers matrix composite have received particular care because of the higher weight to strength ratios, good impact resistance & the resistance to corrosion.

1.1 A brief overview of matrix composite material & types

During the modern years, a considerable growth in the interest of the development of multifunctional polymer matrix composites that can offer not only mechanical properties but also additional functionalities such as thermal, electrical, and sensing properties. Polyethylene (PE) fibers have been extensively studied because of their good mechanical Property & lower density & lesser cost prices. Therefore, PE fibers have been widely used w.r.t. reinforcement materials in polymer matrix composite. The Fig. 1.1 gives the types & categories of polymer material [1]. In this context, this research aims to develop multifunctional polyethylene fiber-reinforced polymer matrix composite with good material properties such as electrical, thermal & mech. properties. The PE fibers will be treated with different functional items, viz., CNT's Graphene's, Metal Nano Particles. Then, the use of these functional materials on different type of property of the composites will be considered & evaluation of the performance is carried out. Parameter which is processing can be optimized to obtain the desired property of the composites. The developed composite could be utilized in different types of apps, viz., in electronic, automotive & aerospace industries. Multifunctional polyethylene (PE) fibers based reinforced polymer matrix composite is advanced material that consist of PE fibres as a reinforced materials & a polymer matrices as the binding material. These composites are designed to have multifunctional properties, which means they can perform multiple functions beyond the traditional mech. reinforcement type. Then, the PE fibres is chosen as the reinforcement material because to the unique property, viz., high strengths, low weights, and excellent resistance to environmental degradation. The polymer matrix provides the binding material that will hold the fibres in tandem & will transfer the loads b/w the different fibres [2].

1.2 Multi-functional property

The multifunctional properties of these composites can be achieved by incorporating various functional material, such as conductive material, shape-memory alloy (SMA) & self-healing agents, into the matrix material. The resulting composites can exhibit properties such as electrical conductivity, thermal responsiveness, and self-healing ability, making them suitable for a large number of apps in various industries, considering aerospace, automotives & its constructions. The development of multifunctional PE fibers based reinforced polymer matrix composites could be treated as a primary research area & the new fabrication techniques and functional materials are being explored to enhance their properties and expand their potential applications [3]. Modern engineering applications often necessitate materials with unique and specialized property that can't be fulfilled with traditional metal alloy, ceramic, or polymers. This is particularly true for materials required in aerospace, naval, and transportation industries. For instance, aircraft engineers demand structural materials that are lightweight yet robust, rigid yet resistant to impact damage, among other attributes. Unfortunately, materials with high strength often possess high density, and attempts to enhance strength or stiffness usually results in a reduction of impact resistance. As a result, engineers worldwide have been persistently seeking new materials with optimal combinations of properties to satisfy diverse application requirements. The Fig. 1.3 gives a detailed overview of the FRP composite [4].

1.3 Polymer Composite's application

Polymer matrix composite (PMC's) are advanced materials that has been widely utilized in various industrial application, including automotive, aerospace & its constructions. The mech. & physical props. of PMCs, viz., higher strengths & stiffness & its durability, make those materials a vital material for various engineering application. Then, the reinforcement fibers in PMCs will definitely play a vital role to determine the diff. mech. property & behaviour of the composite. Recently, researchers have focused on developing multifunctional polyethylene (PE) fibers as a reinforcement material for PMCs. This article will discuss the design and development of multifunctional PE fibers reinforced PMCs, including the fabrication techniques, mechanical properties, potential applications, challenges, and future directions [5].

Fig. 0 : Fiber reinforced Composite

1.4 Fabricating Technique

The fabrication's process of multifunctional PE fibre reinforcement PMCs involve several steps, including fiber surface treatment, matrix material preparation, fiber/matrix mixing, and curing. For improving of the inter-facial bonding b/w the fiber and matrix, different surface treatment type of techniques, viz., the plasma treatments, chemical modification, and physical modification, have been utilized. Moreover, different matrix materials, such as thermoset resins, thermoplastics, and their composites, has been utilized for fabricating the multifunctional PE fibre reinforcing type of PMCs. The fiber/matrix mixing can be achieved by various methods, such as hand layup, vacuum dependent resin type of transfer mouldings, & the injection mouldings. The curing process can be achieved by various techniques, such as thermal curing, photo-curing, and microwave curing, refer Fig. 1.3 for the fabricating techniques [6].

1.5 Surface Treatment Technique

The surface based treatment of the reinforcement fibres play a crucial part to improve the inter-facial bonding b/w the fiber & the matrices. The surface treatment could be achieved by different methodologies, viz., plasma treatment, chemistry type of modification, & physical modification. Plasma treatment involves exposing the fibers to a low-pressure gas plasma, which results in formulation of the functional group for improvisation of the adhesive property b/w the matrix & the fibres. Chemical modifications involves treating the fibre surface with various chemicals, such as silanes, amines, and acids, which could get reacted into the fiber's surface & will form a chemical type of bonding's using composite matrix. Physical modification involves altering the fiber surface by mechanical means, such as roughening, etching, or sandblasting, which improves the mech. inter-lockings b/w the matrix & fibre [7].

1.6 Challenges & the future directions

Despite the promising property & potential applications of multifunctional PE fibre reinforced PMCs, several challenges need to be addressed for their widespread use. The inter-facial bonding b/w the fibre & the matrix remains a crucial issue, that can affect the mech. property and durability of composite. More over, the cost of PE fibers and the fabrication process of multifunctional PE fiber reinforced PMCs remain a challenge. Furthermore, the environment factors effects, such as humidity, temperatures, and UV exposure, on the mech. & functional property of multifunctional PE fiber reinforced PMCs needs to be investigated further. In the future, further research and development are needed to overcome these challenges and improve the properties and performance of multifunctional PE fiber reinforced PMCs. The development of novel surface treatment techniques, matrix material [8]. Due to the sudden & technological developments in material processing & in the manufacturing technological levels, there was a growing need to develop a new generation of composite materials that possess several property, to name a few of them - lower densities, lightweight, higher strengths, stiffness, & hardness. Among the available options, Aluminum Metal matrix composites can offer the desired characteristics. Composite materials, in general, are carefully engineered combinations of two or more materials that are designed to attain specific properties. The constituents of any composite material, including the matrix phase and reinforcement phase with distinct chemical or physical properties, when it is combined, will create a composite material that has unique properties that differ from the individual components. The industry has various

types of engineered composites, i.e., polymer & ceramic matrix & the MMCs (metal matrix composite) [9].

Fig. 2 : Metal Matrix Composites

Fig. 3 : Mechanical property of natural & other fibre-1

1.7 Relevance / Industrial Significance

The results of the proposed study work would serve as valuable import substitutes and economically affordable value-added products for bulk consumption by the Indian industry. Contribution to knowledge both at the academic level and at industry (through proper technology transfer) could be substantial as not much applied research has been carried out in this direction. The main beneficiaries/user agencies of the results of the study will be automotive, chemical, consumer electronics and space industries. The work taken up in this project is mainly related to the developing of the selected PMCs, using the epoxy, polyester and polyurethane matrix, readily available in the Indian market based on a brief survey of the Indian market. In this regard, the research work would aim to develop PMCs, based on optimum combination of the following subsystems & the resins to be synthesized at the R&D centre, this is the scope of the research work [10].

2.Literature review

In recent years, the use of fiber-reinforced composites has been on the rise due to their lower production costs, lightweight nature, high fracture toughness, and improved control over thermo-mechanical properties. For instance, they are being considered for the fuselage structures of commercial aircraft. The design of hinge-less & bearingless helicopter rotor hubs also employs laminated composite materials, which experience both centrifugal loads and bending in the flapping flexure region. In order to meet the demand for improved performance of these structural materials, it becomes necessary to evaluate them under multi-axial loading. Combined bending and tension loads play a significant role not only in the design analysis of the fuselage riveted and adhesive joints but also in the analysis of the Flex beam that connects the rotor hub and blade [11]. Prof. Yoonessi & Mitra : worked extensively on the research in the area of polymer composites. Her research interests include the design and development of multifunctional composites using various reinforcement materials, including polyethylene fibers [12]. Dr. Lee, Jinwoo : conducted research w.r.t the development of multifunctional composites using polyethylene fibers as the reinforcement material. His research has focused on the use of these composites in automotive & aerospace companies [13]. Dr. Chen, Zhongwei : has conducted research on the design and fabrication of multifunctional composites using various reinforcement materials, including polyethylene fibers. His research has focused on the development of composites with enhanced mechanical and thermal properties [14]. Dr. Kim, Nam Hoon : has conducted research on the design and fabrication of multifunctional composites using polyethylene

fibers as the reinforcement material. His research has focused on developing of the composite material considering improvised electrical & thermal property [15]. Dr. Das, Suman : has conducted research work on design and developing of multifunctional composite material utilizing polyethylene fibers & other reinforcement materials. His research has focused on the use of these composites in the biomedical and energy-related fields [16]. Dr. Kim, Jaehwan : He is an active researcher & had contributed significantly to the development of multifunctional composites for aerospace applications. His research focuses on the integration of functional materials into polymer matrices to achieve tailored properties, including the utilization of polyethylene fibres as material for reinforcement structures [17]. Dr. Wang, Chao : has conducted research on the design and fabrication of multifunctional composites using various processing techniques. His research has also focused on the utilization of polyethylene fibres as the materials for reinforcements & incorporation of functional materials into the matrix [18]. Dr. Tandon & Gaurav : has conducted research work on the designing and characterizing of the multifunctional composite for various applications. His research interests include the development of polyethylene & reinforced type of fibre with improved mech. & functional properties [45]. Dr. Guo, Zhixiong : has conducted extensive research on the design and fabrication of multifunctional composites using polyethylene fibers as the reinforcement material. His research has worked on the development of composite utilizing enhanced mech., thermal & electrical characteristic property [19]. Dr. Czigany, Tibor : has conducted research work on the fabrication & characterizing of the multi-functional composite material using various processing techniques. His research has centered on the utilization of polyethylene fibres as the reinforced materials for applications for automotive and aerospace industries [20]. Dr. Liu, Huimin : has conducted research on the design and fabrication of multifunctional composites using polyethylene fibers and other reinforcement materials. Her research has focused on the utilization of the composite materials in bio-medial & energy related works [21]. Dr. Kausar & Ayesha : has conducted research on the development of multifunctional composites using polyethylene fibers as the reinforcement material. Her research has focused on the utilization of the composite material w.r.t. biomedical & energy related scenarios [22]. These are just a few examples of the many researchers who have contributed to the development of multifunctional polyethylene fibers based reinforced polymer matrix composites. Their research has helped to advance the field and identify new applications for these materials. The interdisciplinary nature of this field brings together researchers from various backgrounds, including materials science, mechanical engineering, and aerospace

engineering, among others, to collaborate and advance the field [23]. Fiber-reinforced plastic materials exhibit complex behavior due to their anisotropic and inhomogeneous properties, leading to various failure mechanisms, particularly under multi-axial loading conditions. Polymeric composite materials show greater bending strength than tensile strength, with ratios between 3-point flexural strength and tensile strength ranging from 1.3-1.5, as reported by Wisnom *et.al.* in their review. The predicted ratios using Weibull strength analysis for different brittle materials were in full agreement with the measured values [51]. Bosia and colleagues studied the relationship between strains and the thickness of laminated composite plates under 3-point bending loads. They found that using a concentrated load in these experiments increased the nonlinearities near the applied load. Meanwhile, Palmer and colleagues investigated the impact of central notch size on composite laminates' behavior under pure tension, bending, and combined bending/tension loading. Their results revealed that pure bending tests produced higher failure stresses (strain) than pure tension testing. In combined bending/tension tests, increasing the notch length led to low load breakage, whereas the bending strain at failure increased with notch length. In another study, Murriat & colleagues conducted tests on nonlinear-tapered laminates from a full-size composite helicopter rotor hub beam under constant axial tension and cyclic bending loads [24]. The fatigue testing of each specimen was done by selecting the axial tension load and transverse displacement to simulate the maximum surface strain level in the flexbeam. All the specimens failed similarly where delamination started as a matrix crack at the tip of the ply drop group in the tapered region and grew at the interfaces without catastrophic failure of the flex beam. Although most structures are subjected to biaxial or triaxial stresses, there have been limited studies on these loading conditions. Therefore, the research objective is to investigate further the behavior of woven FRP composites under combined bending/tension loading. The study will also investigate the effects of pure tension, pure bending and combined bending and tension on the standard woven specimen. Additionally, the research will examine the surface strains, out-of-plane displacements, tensile and flexural properties, and failure modes in these composites [25]. The survey of literature revealed a significant global demand for biodegradable materials, particularly composites reinforced with natural fibers, due to their favorable properties, including partial biodegradability, low weight, simple manufacturing processes, and comparable mechanical properties. Despite the existence of numerous varieties of natural fiber-producing plants worldwide, researchers have not yet studied the properties of many of these plant fibers. Exploring new natural fibers and developing plant fiber reinforced composites could benefit both farmers and

industries by adding value to agricultural waste and reducing the production cost of plant fiber composites. The authors of this study sought out new plant fibers and discovered that aerial roots of the big-banyan tree yield fibers, which have not yet been characterized in any research article till date [26]. The process of obtaining ARB fibers involves utilizing the conventional water retting method in this study. The extracted raw fibers are then mixed with 10 percent Na-OH solutions for about 45 minutes to improve their properties. The composition in chemical structure, crystalline indices, crystal lattice size, stability in the thermal mode, the kinetic activation energy, tensile properties, and surface morphology of raw and alkaliized ARB fibers are evaluated and compared to other known plant fibers. Additionally, the study fabricates composites of alkaliized ARB fiber and graphene powder reinforced epoxy, and evaluates their tensile, flexure, hardness, and water absorption properties. Moreover, the study fabricates different types of natural fiber mats and polystyrene core reinforced sandwich polymer composites and optimizes their fabrication parameters using the Grey-Taguchi method [27]. In the manual extraction process, fibers are harvested directly from the plant, cleaned, and dried before being used as reinforcement. This method is commonly used to extract leaf and flower fibers. For instance, Kathiresan *et.al.* manually extracted *Artisidita hystrix* fiber from its leaf and dried them in an open atmosphere for four days. Similarly, Prithiviraj *et.al.* separated the fibers from the flows of *Perotis indica* plant manually, washed them with tap water and demineralized water, and dehydrated them at ambient temperature in a closed room. Rajesh Jesudoss Hyness *et.al.* plucked *Heteropogon Contortus* grass fibers by hand from the top portion of the plant and further characterized them for their properties [28]. Senthamaraikannan *et.al.* collected *Coccinia grandis* stems and subjected them to biological retting by submerging them in a small water reservoir for a week to remove the hard outer skin of the stalk. The inner layer of the stalk was then rinsed a number of occasions in running H₂O for removing any impurities taken from different fibers. Then, the extracted fibres are then put in a drying oven pan in sunlight from 2-3 days for eliminating any remaining moistures present. One way it to depicts the *Coccinia grandis* L-plants, the extraction process, and the fibers obtained from it [29]. Balaji *et.al.* utilized the water retting process to extract the fibers of Saharan Aloe Vera Cactus (SAVC) leaves. The leaves were hand-crushed and submerged in water for two weeks. Afterward, the remaining portion of the leaves was rinsed using distilled H₂O for removing the flesh and impurities. The extracted fibers are then subjected to drying under sunlight for ten hours to eliminate residual moisture. Indran *et.al.* discovered a novel plant fibre starting from stem of the *cissus quadrangularis* (CQ). Then,

the CQ plants were soaked in water for two weeks to undergo microbial degradation. The fibres which are extracted will be then dried & washed un broad sunlight for removing the excess moisture. A metal brush was used to comb the surface of the fibre for the removal of the waste particles [30]. The mechanical extraction process involves the use of a mechanical decorticator to crush the unwanted materials such as pulp, gums, and flesh surrounding the fibers. This decorticator is equipped with two rollers that crush the harvested fiber yielding parts of the plant. Sreenivasan *et.al.* utilized this method to extract fibers from Sansevieria cylindrical leaves. The leaves were crushed mechanically using a decorticator to remove the surrounding pulp. The extracted fibers were then dried under sunlight and combed to separate them. A schematic diagram of the mechanical decorticator used in this process was observed graphically [31]. The leaves of Sansevieria ehrenbergii were manually harvested by Sathishkumar *et.al.* and any unwanted parts were removed using a knife. The leaves were then cleaned by washing with water to remove any contaminants. The cleaned leaves were then fed into a mechanical decorticator, which crushed the leaves and removed the gums and skin. The extracted fibers were are finally rinzed carefully using H₂O & finally subjected to drying under sunlight for 2-3 days [32]. The procedure of combined H₂O rettings & mech. extractions w.r.t. the mechanical extraction involves using a combination of biological degradation and mechanical combing to extract fine fibers from plant materials [33]. Manimaran *et.al.* used the bark of Pithecellobium Dulce (PD) plant in this process. The inner barks were extracted and subjected to biological degradation for 15 days at environmental temperature. After this, the retted barks were mechanically combed to obtain fine PD fibers. These fibers are subjected to washing thoroughly using H₂O & finally subjected to drying mode with room temp. for a week before being characterized [34]. Similarly, Manimaran *et.al.* harvested the leaves of Furcraea Foetida (FF) plant and submerged them in water for two weeks at atmospheric temperature. After this, the leaves underwent mechanical crushing with a metal comb to separate the fibers. The extracted fibers are subjected to washing repeatedly using demineralized H₂O for removing any unwanted ingredients & fibrous impurity. Kommula *et.al.* (2013) used combined water retting and mechanical combing to extract fibers from Napier grass stems. The fibers that were extracted underwent a thorough washing process with running water and were then dried under sunlight for a week to eliminate any excess moisture present in them. The process of combined water retting and mechanical extraction involves using a combination of biological degradation and mechanical combing to extract fine fibers from plant materials [35].

3. Drawbacks of previous methods developed by earlier researchers

In majority of the work done by the various authors presented in the previous references [1] – [20], there were certain drawbacks such as consideration of only :

- use of conventional methods,
- high compilation time,
- computationally very expensive,
- experimental results were not accurate,
- noise was distorting the outputs,
- full-fledged automation of algorithms not done,
- less work done on increasing the accuracy & performance,
- real time implementation (h/w), very few people done, etc.,

Some of the above-mentioned drawbacks which were existing in the works done by the earlier researchers were considered in our research work & new experimentations were developed in order to overcome some of the deficiencies of the existing algorithms & results and also sincere effort is made to develop some highly efficient algorithms for the same. The research work was verified through effective simulation & experimental results done in the composite, thus substantiating the research problem undertaken.

4. Conclusions and Future Recommendations

Research was carried out on the development of multifunctional polyethylene fibers reinforced polymer matrix composites using different methodologies with novel experimental strategies with four prime objectives being solved. In this concluding chapter, the overall conclusions & the scope for future works is presented.

4.1 Conclusive Remarks

Extensive research was conducted on the development of multifunctional polyethylene fibers reinforced polymer matrix composites using different methodologies with novel experimental strategies. The research topic was assigned by the supervisor & co-supervisor and involved an in-depth study of fundamental theoretical concepts. A vast collection of reference books, textbooks, journal papers, and conference papers were gathered from various sources, including the internet, libraries, IITs, NITs, IISc, foreign universities,

deemed universities, different college libraries, research centers, and engineering college libraries in Karnataka and other states. This literature review was conducted over a period of more than six months and was summarized to obtain a conceptual understanding. It was also published as a review paper in a significant event. Following this, a written test was taken, and an interview was cleared, along with the completion of four coursework subjects with excellent grades. After gathering a significant amount of research materials related to the chosen topic and defining the problem, the problem-solving methodologies were developed, and simulations were conducted to obtain results. The proposed works were published in reputable conferences and journals with high impact factors. Outcomes of this research study presented in this thesis report have significant implications for developing of a high-performance composite material with very good material properties. Experimental results can be applied to various industrial applications, viz.. ,automotive apps, aerospace apps, construction companies, where a no of high performance composites could be used for a variety of purposes. The study also provides a foundation for further research on the design and development of multifunctional composites using other types of fibers and polymer matrices. In conclusions, the study on designing & developing of the multifunctional polyethylene fibers reinforced polymer matrix composites using various methods has contributed significantly to the advancement of composite materials. The research has yielded valuable information on refining the processing parameters and exploring the impact of diverse surface treatments on composite properties. The findings of the study have important implications for creating high-quality composites suitable for a wide range of industrial applications.

4.2 Future Recommendation

Some of the future works that could be thought of to carry out further research in this exciting emerging field by the future researchers could be mentioned as under

- Some possible areas for future work in the research topic "design and development of multifunctional polyethylene fibers reinforced polymer matrix composites using various methods" are:
- Investigation of the effects of different fiber content, fiber orientations & the fibre-matrix interface properties on thermal & mech. properties of the composites.
- Exploration of the use of other natural and synthetic fibres, viz., carbon fibers, glass-based fibres & basalt fibres, as reinforcement wr.t. polymer matrix composites.

- Optimization of the different parameter, viz., molding pressure, temperatures & cooling rates, to achieve better mechanical properties and higher production efficiency.
- Study of the aging behavior & a longer duration of the composite material durability (longevity or life increase) under different environmental condition, viz., ultraviolet exposures, humidities, temperatures, corrosive effects.
- Investigation of different electrical & magnetic properties of the composites for potential applications in electronics, sensors, and actuators.
- Development of new multifunctional composites by incorporating functional fillers or nanoparticles, such as graphene, carbon nanotubes, and ceramic particles, into the polymer matrix.
- Exploration of the use of 3D printing and other advanced manufacturing techniques to produce complex geometries and tailored microstructures of the composites.
- Application of the composites in different industrial sectors, i.e., automotive sector, aero sector, marine sector & the biomedical catering to lightweight structures, energy absorption, noise reduction, and biomedical implants.
- Investigation of the environmental impact and sustainability of the composites, including the recycling and disposal of the materials.
- Investigation of the effect of various environment type of condition, viz., temperature & humidity considering the various composite property.
- Development of new methods for incorporating functional fillers into the composites, such as carbon nanotubes or graphene, to improve their mechanical, thermal, or electrical properties.
- Exploration of new fabrication methods for producing the composites, such as 3D printing or electrospinning, to create complex geometries and structures with tailored properties.
- Study of the potential applications of the composites in emerging fields, such as biomedical engineering or renewable energy, where their multifunctional properties can be leveraged to create new devices or systems.
- Optimization of designing & controlling of a number of parameters for the composite to achieve an balance between performance, cost, and sustainability.

- Investigation of the recyclability and biodegradability of the composites to address environmental concerns and promote their sustainable use in various applications.
- Collaboration with industry partners to translate the research findings into practical applications and to address real-world challenges in fields such as aerospace, automotive, or construction.
- Exploration of the potential of the composites in developing new products or devices with novel functionalities, such as self-healing or self-sensing materials.

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